

CONFLICT MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES OF EMPLOYEES AT WORKPLACE STUDY

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Abstract

Conflict in the workplace cannot be avoided because of varied opinions, goals, and interrelations. Conflict management methods play a vital role in ensuring there is harmony in the workplace, improved teamwork, and organizational success. This research study analyses the employees' conflict management styles in a well-known private manufacturing sector and their consideration towards general attitudes on conflict, intrapersonal conflict scenarios, individual conflict managing styles, organization support, and the effect on work effectiveness due to conflict settlement. By applying a descriptive research design and stratified proportionate random sampling method, 100 workers from different departments were surveyed through a Likert scale-based structured questionnaire. It was found that over half the respondents (55%) indicated low organizational support towards conflict management and 63% of the respondents expressed a low work impact from conflict resolution. Additionally, conflict management training and availability of resources were also inadequate. The research recommends that organizations need to enhance conflict resolution policies, invest in formal training programs, and adopt proactive mediation strategies to enhance workplace relationships. Through a culture of open communication and formal conflict resolution, organizations can reduce workplace conflicts, improve employee well-being, and increase overall productivity.

Keywords: Conflict Management, Workplace Conflict, Conflict Resolution Strategies, Employee Relations, Organizational Support, Mediation, Workplace Harmony, Dispute Resolution, Employee Well-being, Team Collaboration

Introduction:

Conflict is a natural part of any workplace, occurring due to differences in views, objectives, and interpersonal relationships. Proper conflict management is essential to ensure a productive work environment, teamwork, and organizational success. Conflict is an inevitable part of any workplace, arising from differences in opinions, objectives, and interpersonal relationships. Effective conflict management is crucial for fostering

teamwork, maintaining a productive work environment, and ensuring organizational success.

This research investigates the strategies used in conflict management in a reputable private manufacturing industry, a large organization with diverse workers. Through evaluating employees' overall attitudes towards conflict, the level of conflicts in the workplace, and the success of conflict management measures in place,

this study seeks to shed light on how conflicts are managed and their effect on organizational effectiveness. It also investigates variables like gender, marital status, and job designation to establish their effect on conflict management measures. Organizations enact Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace along different dimensions, such as General Perception of Conflict, Conflicts arise at the workplace, Conflict on Work Environment, Personal Conflict Management Strategies Organizational Support and Policies, Organizational Support and Policies, Impact of Conflict on Work and Training and Resources.

The key conflict patterns in the workplace, uncovering employees' attitudes, the presence of organizational support, and the success of conflict management techniques. The findings are useful for organizations to improve their conflict resolution processes, better workplace relationships, and a more harmonious workplace.

Abdul Rahim (2002) describes conflict management as the ability to handle interpersonal disagreements constructively through various styles, such as integrating, obliging, dominating, avoiding, and compromising, which impact relationships and organizational effectiveness. William Wilmot and Joyce Hocker (2007) they define conflict management as the process of recognizing and addressing conflicts effectively, stressing the importance of communication skills, negotiation, and understanding underlying issues.

According to Peter Tjosvold (2008) Conflict Management as the process of fostering constructive conflict in a way that improves teamwork and organizational

effectiveness, emphasizing collaboration to achieve innovative solutions.

Methodology:

Aim:

To study the, "Strategies involved in Conflict Management".

Objectives:

- To analyse the general perception about conflict.
- To inducted the level of conflict in their work environment.
- To highlight the level of present conflict management strategies.
- To reveal the level of organizational support.
- To highlight the overall conflict management strategies of employees in the workplace.

Hypothesis:

- There is no significant difference between the marital status of the respondent and Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at the Workplace.
- There is a no significant difference among the Position in the company of the respondents and Progressive Learning of Employees.
- There is no significant relationship between the position in the company and Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace.

Research Design: This research employs a descriptive research design in order to study the adoption and efficacy of Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at

Workplace. The study centers on studying different aspects of Conflict Management Strategies, such as General Perception of Conflict, Conflicts arise at the workplace, Conflict on Work Environment, Personal Conflict Management Strategies Organizational Support and Policies, Organizational Support and Policies, Impact of Conflict on Work and Training and Resources. Satisfied Proportionate random sampling technique is applied for data collection among employees in various departments. The research applies standardized surveys as a major instrument to gather quantitative feedback on employees' views of Conflict Management Strategies. Statistical techniques are applied in the analysis of survey responses to spot Perception, strategies, and Impact of Conflict Management towards Conflict Management and Strategies.

Universe & Sampling: The universe of the study consists of 6000 employees in a reputable private manufacturing industry. The organization consists of 34 departments, the research adopted the stratified proportionate random sampling technique and selected 3 respondents from each department. This resulted in 102 respondents being selected for the study. Since pre-testing was done with 2 respondents they were excluded and as a result 100 respondents were taken for this study. The sample provided a varied and balanced number of employees for thorough analysis of Conflict Management Strategies. The chosen respondents reveal insightful information on the efficacy and strategies of Conflict at the Organization.

Tools for data collection: The questionnaire is prepared based on a Likert scale to quantitatively evaluate responses to

avoid subjective bias of opinions of Conflict Management Strategies. In the current research for Conflict Management Strategies, it is applied utilizing structured questionnaires as the tool for gathering information. The questionnaire is made up of close-ended questions that are intended to measure employee views, knowledge, and on the Conflict Management Strategies of Employees in important areas including General Perception of Conflict, Conflicts arise at the workplace, Conflict on Work Environment, Personal Conflict Management Strategies Organizational Support and Policies, Organizational Support and Policies, Impact of Conflict on Work and Training and Resources.

Results & Discussion:

Based on the given table 1, it is evident that little more than half (51%) of the respondents have denoted a low general perception of conflict, however less than half (49%) of the respondents have expressed a high level of general perception of conflict. While more than half (54%) of the respondents have denoted a less conflict that may arises at the workplace, however less than half (46%) of the respondents have expressed a high level of conflicts that may arises at the workplace. More than half (54%) of the respondents have denoted a low conflict on Work Environment, however less than half (46%) of the respondents have expressed a high level of conflict on work environment. It is notable that more than half (54%) of the respondents have denoted low personal conflict management strategies. Less than half (46%) of the respondents have expressed a high level of personal conflict management strategies.

Similarly, more than half (55%) of the respondents have denoted a low organizational support and policies in the organization. Less than half (45%) of the

respondents have expressed a good level of organizational support and policies structure. Majority (63%) of the respondents have denoted a low impact of

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents based on overall Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace

Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace	Low	Percentage	High	Percentage
General Perception of Conflict	51	51	49	49
Conflicts arise at the Workplace	54	54	46	46
Conflict on Work Environment	54	54	46	46
Personal Conflict Management Strategies	54	54	46	46
Organizational Support and Policies	55	55	45	45
Impact of Conflict on Work	63	63	37	37
Training and Resources	56	56	44	44
Overall Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace	52	52	48	48

conflict in the work. Less than two-fifth (37%) of the respondents have expressed a high level of impact of conflict on work in their work environment.

However, more than half (56%) of the respondents have denoted a less availability of training and resources. Less than half (44%) of the respondents have expressed a good availability of training and resources in the organization. More than half (52%) of the respondents have denoted a low impact on conflict management strategies of employees at workplace. Less than half (48%) of the respondents have expressed a high-level impact on conflict management strategies of employees at workplace.

From the presented table 2, illustrates that there is a significant difference among the marital status of the respondents and the dimension of organizational support and policies. It is also found that there is no significant

difference among the marital status of the respondents and the dimensions of general perception of conflict, conflicts arise at the workplace, conflict on work environment, personal conflict management strategies, impact of conflict on work and training and resources and overall conflict management strategies of employees at workplace. This indicates that respondents perceive and experience these aspects similarly, suggesting that gender plays a determining role in organisational support and policy. And this also indicates that the marital status respondents perceive and experience these aspects similarly, suggesting that

marital status respondents do not play a determining role in general perception, conflicts arise at the workplace, work environment, personal strategies, impact of conflict on work, training and resource and overall conflict management strategies of employees at workplace.

H0: There is no significant difference among the marital status of the respondent and Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at the Workplace

H1: There is significant difference among the marital status of the respondent and Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at the Workplace

Result: One-way analysis of variance was applied and it was revealed that there is no significant difference between the marital status of the respondents and conflict management strategies of employees at the workplace. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 2. One-way analysis of variance between marital status of the respondents and overall Conflict Management Strategies of employees at workplace

Factors		Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Statistical Inference
General Perception of Conflict	Between Groups	33.502	2	16.751	.344	P>0.05 .710 Not Significant
	Within Groups	4719.888	97	48.659		
	Total	4753.390	99			
Conflicts arise at the workplace	Between Groups	9.865	2	4.932	.291	P>0.05 .748 Not Significant
	Within Groups	1644.135	97	16.950		
	Total	1654.000	99			
Conflict on Work Environment	Between Groups	25.574	2	12.787	1.047	P>0.05 .355 Not Significant
	Within Groups	1184.426	97	12.211		
	Total	1210.000	99			
Personal Conflict Management Strategies	Between Groups	47.750	2	23.875	.591	P>0.05 .556 Not Significant
	Within Groups	3920.410	97	40.417		
	Total	3968.160	99			
Organizational Support and Policies	Between Groups	97.008	2	48.504	2.405	P<0.05 .096 Significant
	Within Groups	1956.382	97	20.169		
	Total	2053.390	99			
Impact of Conflict on Work	Between Groups	2.901	2	1.451	.152	P>0.05 .859 Not Significant
	Within Groups	924.099	97	9.527		
	Total	927.000	99			
Training and Resources	Between Groups	32.123	2	16.062	1.275	P>0.05 .284 Not Significant
	Within Groups	1222.067	97	12.599		

	Total	1254.190	99			
Overall Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace	Between Groups	729.606	2	364.803	.891	P>0.05 .413 Not Significant
	Within Groups	39704.584	97	409.326		
	Total	40434.190	99			

G1 = General Perception of Conflict; **G2** = Conflicts arise at the workplace; **G3** = Conflict on Work Environment; **G4** = Personal Conflict Management Strategies; **G5** = Organizational Support and Policies; **G6** = Impact of Conflict on Work; **G7** = Training and Resources; **G8** = Overall Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace.

From the presented table 3, illustrates that there is a significant difference among the position in the company of the respondents and the dimension of general perception of conflict. It is also found that there is no significant difference among the position in the company of the respondents and the dimensions of conflicts arises at the workplace, conflict on work environment, personal conflict management strategies, organizational support and policies, impact of conflict on work and training and resources and overall conflict management strategies of employees at workplace.

H1: There is a no significant difference among the Position in the company of the

respondents and Progressive Learning of Employees

H0: There is a significant difference among the Position in the company of the respondents and Progressive Learning of Employees

Result: One-way analysis of variance was applied and it was revealed that there is a significant difference among the Position in the company of the respondents and progressive conflict management strategies of employees at the workplace. Hence, the research hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3. One-way analysis of variance between position in the company of the respondents and overall Conflict Management Strategies of employees at workplace

Factors		Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Statistical Inference
General Perception of Conflict	Between Groups	255.518	2	127.759	2.755	P<0.05 .069 Significant
	Within Groups	4497.872	97	46.370		
	Total	4753.390	99			
Conflicts arise at the workplace	Between Groups	46.121	2	23.061	1.391	P>0.05 .254 Not Significant
	Within Groups	1607.879	97	16.576		
	Total	1654.000	99			
Conflict on Work Environment	Between Groups	21.014	2	10.507	.857	P>0.05 .428 Not Significant
	Within Groups	1188.986	97	12.258		
	Total	1210.000	99			

Personal Conflict Management Strategies	Between Groups	81.083	2	40.542	1.012	P>0.05 .367 Not Significant
	Within Groups	3887.077	97	40.073		
	Total	3968.160	99			
Organizational Support and Policies	Between Groups	22.586	2	11.293	.539	P>0.05 .585 Not Significant
	Within Groups	2030.804	97	20.936		
	Total	2053.390	99			
Impact of Conflict on Work	Between Groups	16.461	2	8.231	.877	P>0.05 .419 Not Significant
	Within Groups	910.539	97	9.387		
	Total	927.000	99			
Training and Resources	Between Groups	2.233	2	1.117	.087	P>0.05 .917 Not Significant
	Within Groups	1251.957	97	12.907		
	Total	1254.190	99			
Overall Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace	Between Groups	405.370	2	202.685	.491	P>0.05 .613 Not Significant
	Within Groups	40028.820	97	412.668		
	Total	40434.190	99			

G1 = General Perception of Conflict; **G2** = Conflicts arise at the workplace; **G3** = Conflict on Work Environment; **G4** = Personal Conflict Management Strategies; **G5** = Organizational Support and Policies; **G6** = Impact of Conflict on Work; **G7** = Training and Resources; **G8** = Overall Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace.

From the presented table it is evident that there is a significant relationship between the position in the company of the respondents and the dimensions of General Perception of Conflict. The table also states that there is no significant relationship between the position in the company of the respondents and the dimensions of the study that include; Conflicts arises at the workplace, Conflict on Work Environment, Personal Conflict Management Strategies, Organizational Support and Policies, Impact of Conflict on Work, Training and Resources and Overall Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace of the respondents. This suggests that while the position in the company influences how employees see the

General Perception of Conflict, and it does not significantly impact the Conflicts arises at the workplace, Work Environment, Personal Conflict Management Strategies, Organizational Support and Policies, Impact of Conflict on Work, Training and Resources and Overall Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace of the respondents.

H0: There is no significant relationship between the position in the company and Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace.

Table 4. Correlation between the position in the company of the respondents and the overall dimensions of Conflict Management Strategies of employees at workplace

Variable	Correlation value	Statistical Inference
General Perception of Conflict	.232*	P<0.05 Significant
Conflicts arise at the workplace	.099	P>0.05 Not Significant
Conflict on Work Environment	.058	P>0.05 Not Significant
Personal Conflict Management Strategies	.138	P>0.05 Not Significant
Organizational Support and Policies	.097	P>0.05 Not Significant
Impact of Conflict on Work	.058	P>0.05 Not Significant
Training and Resources	.023	P>0.05 Not Significant
Overall Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace	.035	P>0.05 Not Significant

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

H1: There is a significant relationship between the position in the company and Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace.

Result: The Karl Pearsons correlation test was applied with the variables and it was evident that there is significant relationship between the position in the company and Conflict Management Strategies of Employees at Workplace. Hence, the research hypothesis is accepted the null hypothesis is rejected.

Suggestions: This study's recommendations are based on some key findings. Additionally, studies have shown that the workplace conflicts are common and that employees have varied perceptions of conflict and organizational support.

Suggestions for the organisations: Organizations that want to enhance their

Conflict Management Strategies need to follow a few crucial strategies. To begin with, they must Strengthening Organizational Support and Policies, Enhanced Training and Resources, Customized Conflict Resolution Strategies, Encouraging Open Dialogue, Periodic Conflict Assessments.

As most employees had reported low organizational support, businesses must strengthen conflict resolution policies and provide open communication about available support systems. And as a result of the low availability of training and resources, organizations need to invest in frequent conflict management workshops to make employees proficient in negotiation, communication, and mediation skills. Conflict management approaches will have to vary at different job levels since, based on level in the organization, people might have different conceptions of

conflict. Senior executives need to contribute to a good team-working climate. Fostering open communication culture by encouraging employees to openly discuss their conflicts without threats of punishment is likely to improve the health of the workplace. Organizations must carry out frequent reviews to gauge the effectiveness of current conflict management approaches and make proper adjustments to maximize workplace harmony.

Suggestions for the HRD team: The HRD function must incorporate Conflict Management Strategies practices in recruitment, training, and performance appraisal. They have to develop clear conflict resolution policies, establish a conflict resolution committee, ensure equal access to support systems, regular conflict management training, leadership training for managers, simulation-based learning, tailor strategies for different job levels, encourage mediation programs, promote a culture of open communication, regular one-on-one check-ins, improve interdepartmental collaboration, employee surveys and feedback, monitor workplace conflicts, continuous policy review and improvement. Through the application of these recommendations, the HRD team can build a more supportive, open, and harmonious work environment that ultimately enhances employee satisfaction, productivity, and organizational success.

Communication & Feedback Mechanism: A good mechanism of communication and feedback is crucial to the effective execution of Conflict Management Strategies practices at an organization. In order to properly enact and

improve conflict management processes in the organization, there has to be a process of structured communication and feedback. This process has to allow employees to express concerns, improve upon things, and even have open dialogue with management. The following is a suggested framework for communication and feedback. To encourage employees to share their experiences and challenges related to workplace conflicts, multiple channels should be available like direct supervisor meetings, anonymous feedback forms, open forums & town hall meetings, hr helpdesk & support portal. Feedback should be gathered systematically using periodic employee surveys, focus group discussions, exit interviews. To ensure transparency and accountability in addressing workplace conflicts, the following steps should be followed. reporting conflicts, investigation & resolution, follow-up & continuous monitoring. Since managers and supervisors play a key role in conflict resolution, their input should also be considered as managerial training feedback, peer reviews & 360° feedback. Based on the feedback received, organizations should revise conflict management policies, introduce new training modules, evaluate effectiveness using key performance indicators (KPIs). An organized mechanism of communication and feedback promotes a proactive method of conflict management. By giving workers several means of communication, systematically evaluating feedback, and making policy improvements constantly, organizations are able to promote a more conducive and conflict-enduring work environment.

Current trend of Green HR Practices:

The newest Conflict Management Strategies has developed over time with new practices, with a focus on proactive resolution, employee health, and corporate harmony. Firms are also moving towards more adaptive, inclusive, and technologically supported methods. Some of the new conflict management trends are rather than merely reacting to conflicts when they occur, many organizations are adopting preventative strategies such as routine conflict management training, team-building activities, clear organizational policies, Organizations are increasingly using structured mediation processes to resolve conflicts efficiently and fairly. Technology is being leveraged to enhance conflict resolution strategies, Emotional Intelligence (EQ) in Conflict Resolution, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) in Conflict Resolution, with remote and hybrid work becoming the norm, organizations have had to adapt conflict management strategies, gamification of Conflict Resolution Training.

Suggestions for quality research and design department: The Quality Research and Design (QRD) Department is responsible for ensuring sustainable innovation and operational excellence. To become more effective, the department needs to incorporate Conflict Management Strategies principles into its design and research activities. By conducting regular employee conflict surveys, sentiment analysis of employee feedback, incident tracking system the outcome helps in recognizing recurring conflict triggers and developing targeted interventions. Based on research findings, QRD should propose customized conflict resolution models

specific to the organization's culture like Hybrid Conflict Resolution Models, AI-Powered Predictive Conflict Management Tools, Customized Conflict Resolution Training the Outcome ensures a structured and scalable conflict resolution framework. Conflicts can impact the **quality of work and operational efficiency**. QRD should integrate conflict management into **quality control frameworks** by assessing Conflict's Impact on Work Quality, Root Cause Analysis (RCA) for Workplace Disputes, Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for Conflict Resolution. By combining research, data analysis, technology, and cross-functional collaboration, the QRD department will lead cutting-edge conflict management solutions. Proactive measures will minimize workplace conflict, increase employee satisfaction, and increase overall organizational performance.

Conclusion:

This Conflict Management Strategies in the Workplace study offers important information on how workers experience, see, and manage conflict in an organized organizational setting. The results show that conflict is a normal aspect of the workplace, yet its management is different depending on various factors including general perception, work environment, individual strategies, and organizational support.

One of the most important findings is that most employees indicated low organizational support, training facilities, and personal conflict management techniques. This indicates that firms need to enhance conflict resolution policies, ensure open communication channels, and invest in frequent training programs. Employees at various hierarchical levels also view

conflict differently, with senior-level employees having a more formalized approach than entry-level employees.

Statistical analysis indicates that marital status does not have a significant effect on conflict management approaches, while job position affects the overall attitude toward conflict. This indicates the influence of leadership in the determination of conflict resolution attitudes and behaviors. Correlation analysis also supports that job position influences the perception of conflict but does not have a significant effect on other aspects of conflict management.

In order to promote workplace harmony and productivity, organizations need to implement proactive conflict management strategies, such as routine conflict assessments, formal mediation, open communication, and tailored training. The application of Green HR practices and technology-based conflict management tools can further enhance organizational effectiveness and employee welfare.

Finally, successful management of conflict is critical to a healthy work culture, enhanced employee engagement, and overall organizational effectiveness. Through investment in conflict resolution techniques and creating an open and inclusive communication culture, organizations can prevent workplace conflicts and build a more productive and cohesive workforce.

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